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The musicality of Sounding Objects

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Sounding Objects

- Objects and devices solely intended to produce sound
- Every-day objects that are re-functionalised to make sound
- Sound-producing toys
- “Minor” and toy musical instruments

Usage

- Pastime: making sound alone and in company
- Fundamental part of secular and religious celebrations
- Training instruments
- To participate in music-making.

Trummetta 'e cucuzza

Trummetta 'e cipudda

Trummetta 'e lauru e zirri

Pita (Alessandria del Carretto)

Ecology

When the chestnuts fall in love

- Profound relationships with the landscape and its human and non-human agents.
- Mark the passing of time and the seasons
- Imitate natural sound and allow to communicate with animals and other non-human agents.

Mimesis

Ritual sound

Trocca (Nocera Terinese)

Cordata (Diamante)

Jam a scuntrè Marz (Villapiana)

San Leone (Saracena)

Bells for herd animals

- Functional to keep track of the animals in a herd
- Information on the position and activity of each animal
- Aesthetic function: the herd must produce a pleasurable harmony
- Marker of the family identity
- Bells assigned according to animal rank and personality
- Marker of the animal identity
- Symbolic meaning

Transhumance

Musicality

- “Skills and sensitivity in performing or perception in appreciating music” (Macquarie Dictionary)
- “Sensitivity to, knowledge of, or talent for music” (Merriam-Webster)
- Musicality refers to the uniquely human constellation of skills underlying our ability to perceive, appreciate, and produce music (Sandra E. Trehub 2023)
- **Musicians:** possess perceptive and productive musical abilities
- **Non-musicians:** possess only receptive musical abilities

Components of Musicality

- Relative pitch (e.g., contour and interval analysis),
- Regularity and beat perception,
- Tonal encoding of pitch
- Metrical encoding of rhythm
- Discriminate, identify and predict key features and structures
- Categorize melodic sequences that are similar and different
- Identify relevant pitch and timing differences
- Memorise and recognise melodies
- Sing or play from memory
- Emotional, social, symbolic engagement with and through music

(Rickard and Chin 2017; Trehub 2023; Honing 2018; Müllensiefen et al. 2014)

The musicality of sounding objects

- Children's musical world
- Propaedeutic to musical activity
- Participating in musical activity
- Allow people to express themselves through sound
- Aesthetic connotations
- Communicate social and symbolic meaning
- Initiate ecologic relationships
- Imitate and reproduce complex sonic structures

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